

Synergistic extraction of uranium(VI) in presence of 2,2'-dipyridyl and neutral donors by absorption spectrophotometric method

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The extraction behaviour of uranyl ion from dilute nitric acid medium employing 2,2'-dipyridyl and their mixture with several neutral donor, viz. trioctyl phosphine oxide (TOPO), tributyl phosphine oxide (TBPO), triphenyl phosphine oxide (TPPO), tributyl phosphate (TBP), trioctyl amine (TOA) and Amberlite LA-2 was investigated. The extraction constant ($\log k_{ex}$) for the binary species $[UO_2(dipy)(NO_3)_2(H_2O)_2]$ was determined to be 14.06. The overall extraction constant ($\log K$) for the ternary species for various donors are : 15.55 (TOPO), 15.49 (TBPO), 15.44 (TPPO), 15.35 (TBP), 17.14 (TOA) and 17.11 (Amberlite LA-2).

It is well known that the combination of a β -diketone and an oxodonor enhances the extraction of metal ion many-folds¹ thereby making it possible to carry out the separation from relatively stronger acidic media. Therefore, it was thought of interest to investigate the extraction behaviour of uranyl ion using a mixture of dipy, an oxodonor and amine donors. The present study deals with the synergistic extraction of uranyl ion with dipy in the presence of different oxo-phosphorus and amine donors dissolved in chloroform using absorption spectroscopic technique.

Materials and methods :

A.R. grade 2,2'-dipyridyl (E. Merck) and uranyl nitrate (E. Merck) were used for the present investigations. Trioctyl phosphine oxide (TOPO), tributyl phosphine oxide (TBPO), triphenyl phosphine oxide (TPPO), tributyl phosphate (TBP), trioctyl amine (TOA) and Amberlite LA-2 and other chemicals and solvents were all reagent grade. Spectrophotometric measurements were carried out in a Shimadzu UV-160A spectrophotometer. A Sambros digital pH meter were used for pH measurements.

In the general extraction procedure, a solution containing ~36 g uranium kept in nitrate medium, was equilibrated with dipy in $CHCl_3$. After equilibrium, phases were separated and measured for their metal content colorimetrically using oxine reagent² taking the usual precautions. Distribution co-efficient (D) was calculated from $D = [U^{VI}]_{org}/[U^{VI}]_{aq}$. For the study of synergistic extraction, the organic phase was mixed with base reagent and dipy at varying concentrations. Effect of pH on the enhancement of

uranium extraction was studied by varying pH of the aqueous solution using appropriate reagents. The effects of various diluents on the extent of synergism, were also studied.

Results and discussion

For the extraction of uranium(VI) with dipy, an equilibrium is established within ten minutes of time. Ligand concentration variation experiments were carried out in different concentrations range $2 \times 10^{-3} - 1 \times 10^{-2} M$. It has been shown that % extraction increases with increasing ligand concentration suggesting that more and more stripping of H_2O molecule take place from hydrated sphere of UO_2^{2+} ion by the ligand. The plot of $\log D_0$ vs $\log [dipy]$ yields a straight line with slope ~ 1 suggesting that only one dipy molecule is involved in the binary adduct.

In absence of ligands, neutral donor variation experiments were carried out in the concentration range $2 \times 10^{-3} - 1 \times 10^{-2} M$ at a fixed pH = 5.00 (Table 1). It has been found that % extraction is increased with increase in concentration of the donors. It also points out that % extraction is much higher in cases of the amines than that of the phosphorus donors. This is obvious due to the fact that nitrogen is less electronegative compared to that of the oxygen atom making its lone pair much more available for donation to the metal ion.

H^+ ion concentration variation experiment for the ternary extraction system $[UO_2(dipy)(TOPO)(NO_3)_2(H_2O)]$ was carried out at a fixed $[dipy] = 2 \times 10^{-3} M$ and fixed concentration of TOPO (Table 1). It has been found that the ex-

tent of extraction enhances with decrease in pH. This may be explained by the fact that at higher pH some H₂O molecules are complexed with the UO₂²⁺ ion making much less donor capability during the time of synergistic extraction. A moderate pH of 5.00 was chosen for our experiment.

Table 1. Synergistic extraction of UO₂²⁺ by mixture of dipy and donors (concentration of dipy = 0.002 M, pH = 5.00 and solvent = chloroform)

Donor	Concentration of donors, M	D	% Extraction	S.C.	log β
TOPO	0.008	4.929	83.50	1.243	1.51
	0.006	3.878	79.53	1.221	1.50
	0.004	2.705	72.90	1.208	1.49
	0.002	1.406	58.91	1.152	1.47
TBPO	0.008	4.804	82.70	1.226	1.44
	0.006	3.628	78.26	1.217	1.43
	0.004	2.614	72.22	1.200	1.43
	0.002	1.190	54.33	1.138	1.42
TBP	0.008	3.446	78.38	1.156	1.31
	0.006	2.373	70.32	1.062	1.29
	0.004	1.010	50.25	0.925	1.27
	0.002	0.758	43.70	0.763	1.29
TPPO	0.008	4.754	82.60	1.217	1.40
	0.006	3.323	76.85	1.116	1.39
	0.004	2.233	69.08	1.033	1.38
	0.002	1.100	52.63	0.928	1.37

Table 2. Synergistic extraction of UO₂²⁺ by mixture of dipy and donors (concentration of dipy = 0.002 M, pH = 5.00 and solvent = chloroform)
Synergistic extraction of

Donor	Concentration of donor, M	D	% Extraction	S.C.	log β
TOA	0.0008	9.679	90.62	1.280	3.10
	0.0006	6.666	86.99	1.256	3.09
	0.0004	4.538	81.94	1.217	3.08
	0.0002	3.357	77.05	1.193	3.07
Amberlite LA-2	0.0008	9.510	90.47	1.265	3.03
	0.0006	5.929	86.26	1.248	3.02
	0.0004	4.013	80.05	1.210	3.01
	0.0002	3.001	75.13	1.173	3.00

Synergistic extraction studies :

The synergistic extraction studies of UO₂²⁺ ion by dipy and neutral donors was carried out in aqueous nitric acid at pH = 5.0 for the donors under study. The plot log (D - D₀) vs log [donor] yields a straight line (Fig. 1) with slope ~1 suggesting the nature of the extracted species as : [UO₂(dipy)(Donor)(NO₃)₂(H₂O)]. The synergistic co-efficient (S.C.) for the combination of any two extractants 1 and 2 have been defined as

$$S.C. = \log [D_{mix}/(D_1 + D_2)] \quad (1)$$

where D_{mix}, D₁ and D₂ denote the distribution ratios of a metal ion with mixture of extractants (1 and 2), extractant (1) and extractant (2), respectively in ternary liquid system.

Table 3. Equilibrium constants for binary as well as ternary extraction system

System	log k _{ex} (average)	Donor	log K	log K _s
UO ₂ ²⁺ - DP	14.06	TOPO	15.55	1.49
		TBPO	15.49	1.43
		TPPO	15.44	1.38
		TBP	15.35	1.29
		TOA	17.14	3.08
		Amberlite LA-2	17.11	3.02

In present case S.C. is defined as

$$S.C. = \log [D/(D_0 + D_s)] \quad (2)$$

Stability constant (β) is given by

$$\beta = (D - D_0)/(D_0 \times [Donor]) \quad (3)$$

Here D, D₀ and D_{Donor} are the distribution co-efficients of UO₂²⁺ ion in presence of mixed extractants, dipyridyl alone and donor alone respectively and [Donor] = molar concentration of donor. When mixed extractants were used, it was observed that the extent of metal ion extraction increased rapidly when amine donors are used. So the trend of S.C. and β values also follow the order of amine donors > phosphorus donors (Tables 1 and 2). Among the phosphorus donors the values of S.C. and β values follow the trend TOPO > TBPO > TPPO > TBP and among amines TOA (tertiary amine) > Amberlite LA-2 (secondary amine). Thus the change in the nature of substitution in the donor can easily cause a relatively appreciable change in the analytical parameters like S.C. and β. This is because nitrogen atom is less electronegative compared to the oxygen atom, thus its electron pair is more labile compared to that of oxygen atom making its higher donor capability. In the oxophosphorus donor the following sequence is observed : TOPO > TBPO > TPPO > TBP. This trend is in accordance with the basicity of the oxophosphorus donors and

Fig. 1. Plot of log [D - D₀] vs log [Donor] for synergistic extraction : (■) TOPO, (●) TBPO, (Δ) TBP, (▽) TPPO, (◆) TOA, (●) Amberlite LA-2.

Note

the electronic effect of the alkyl substituents of the phosphorus donors. Among the amine donors, TOA performs better extraction compared to Amberlite LA-2. Though due to the presence of three bulky alkyl groups conformation in TOA (3° amine) is sterically restricted, over Amberlite LA-2 (secondary amine), it is electronically favoured over Amberlite LA-2. Thus here electronic factors favour over the steric factor. Presence of three alkyl groups enhances the availability of the lone pair on the nitrogen atom by the +R effect. Table 3 shows the log values of equilibrium constants k_{ex} (for binary system i.e. only dipy and UO_2^{2+}), equilibrium constant K (for ternary system i.e. UO_2^{2+} -dipy-donors) and equilibrium constant K_S (for adduct formation reaction). It is clearly seen that the log k_{ex} , log K and log K_S values for amine donors (TOA and Amberlite LA-2) are much higher compared to the oxo-phosphorus donors. Among the phosphorus oxides donors the equilibrium values do change appreciably. This fact indicates that the change of substitution in the phosphorus donor or among the amines have some effect in equilibrium constant values (though the effect is not very pronounced). The higher equilibrium constant values of amines again hints the fact that due to low electronegativity of N atom, they can perform as better donors than 'O' donor site of phosphorus donors. The formation of mixed complex by uranium-dipyridyl in presence of phosphorus bases (TOPO)

was also supported by IR measurement of organic extracts. The presence of metal oxygen bond (759 cm^{-1}) and shift of ν_{P-O} of TOPO from 1145 to 1090 cm^{-1} and of ν_{C-N} of dipy from 1580 to 1560 cm^{-1} were recorded in IR data³. The results indicate the involvement of donor molecules in metal complex in organic phase which are in conformity with the distribution data. Actinide ions can expand their coordination shell and so accommodate further donor molecules in their inner sphere, in addition to the dipyridyl groups already present, resulting in enhancement of organophilicity of the mixed complex and subsequently to an increase the extent of extraction into organic solvent.

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